

and are now under investigation at C. R. R. I., Cuttack, by pot application.

TABLE-1

Sl. No.	R ¹	R ²	R ³	M.P. (°C)	% Yield	Concn. in parts per million	% of inhibition of spore germination
1.	Ph	H	COOH	189	70	1000	95
2.	Ph	NO	COOH	162	95	250	100
3.	Ph	Br	COOH	132	65	1000	80
4.	H	H	COOH	205	70	1000	75
5.	H	NO	COOH	240	90	500	100
6.	H	Br	COOH	195	65	1000	85

Compounds No. 1 and 4 are prepared by the carboxylation method described⁵ for resorcinol and also by the method reported elsewhere⁷. The products from both the methods are found to be identical. Compounds No. 2, 5 and 3, 6 are prepared by the methods of nitrosation and bromination respectively as reported earlier^{1,2} from this laboratory. The elemental analysis of all the compounds are quite satisfactory.

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References

1. B. NANDA, S. PADMANAVAN, B. TRIPATHY and A. S. MITTRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 533.
2. A. NAYAK, S. DAS, C. R. MISHRA and A. S. MITTRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 485.
3. S. RAO and A. S. MITTRA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, **15B**, 1062.
4. S. K. MOHANTY, R. SRIDHAR, S. Y. PADMANAVAN, S. RAO and A. S. MITTRA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, **15B**, 1146.
5. T. S. GORE, P. K. INAMDAR and P. M. NAGARKAR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, **12**, 946.
6. A. MOORE and J. MOUTGOMERY, *J. Promol. Hort. Sci.*, 1938, **15**, 253.
7. H. AMAL and A. OZGER, *Rev. faculte Sci. Univ. Istanbul*, 1951, **16A**, 71, through *Chemical Abstract*; 1952, **46**, 4534.
8. N. B. DAS and A. S. MITTRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (communicated.)

Studies on Tripropyltin Dithiocarbamates

T. N. SRIVASTAVA and RASHMI BALA RASTOGI

Department of Chemistry, Lucknow University, Lucknow

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IN continuation to our studies on diorgano dithiocarbamates of organometal moieties, we report the preparation, characterisation, and structure of some new tripropyltin dithiocarbamates of the general formula (Pr₃Sn₂dtc) (where dtc = morpholine-, piperidine-, dibutyl-, N-methylaniline-, diethyl-, N-methylaniline-dithiocarbamates).

Experimental

Bis(tri-propyltin) oxide was obtained from Alfa Inorganics (U.S.A.). Amines and solvents were purified by conventional methods. Physico-chemical measurements were made as reported earlier¹.

A representative method for the preparation of tripropyltin morpholine dithiocarbamate is given below:—

To a mixture of bis(tri-propyltin) oxide (10 mmole) and carbon disulphide (10 ml) in chloroform (20 ml), morpholine (20 ml) in the same solvent (10 ml) was added dropwise at ~ -20°. After 2 hrs. stirring, the excess of chloroform was distilled off at reduced pressure and the residual liquid was extracted with ether which on distillation yielded yellow oily tripropyltin morpholine dithiocarbamate. Yield 70%.

Results and Discussion

Tripropyltin dithiocarbamates have been prepared by the following reaction:—

The reactions were carried out in an organic solvent such as chloroform, benzene or methanol. The analytical data presented in the Table 1 agree well with the proposed stoichiometry. The compounds are high boiling oily liquids, soluble in common organic solvents such as benzene, methanol, acetone and diethylether. Molecular weight determination by cryoscopic method and electrical conductance studies in absolute methanol indicate that the compounds are monomers and non-electrolytes in solution. They are stable at room temperature.

The infrared spectra have been examined in KBr, nujol and solution and it has been observed that there is neither matrix interaction nor changes in solution. An examination of C-N stretchings in infrared spectra of the compounds at $1465 \pm 15 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, shows that the absorption is sensitive to the

TABLE -1
 ANALYTICAL DATA FOR TRIPROPYL TIN DITHIOCARBAMATES (Pr₃Sn₂)

No.	Compounds etc.	Mol. Wt. Found (Calcd.)	B. Pt. (°C) at ~1 mm pressure	Analysis % Found (Calcd.)			Absorption frequencies (cm ⁻¹)	
				Sn	C	H	C-N	C-S
1.	morpholine	380 (410)	170-180	29.06 (29.02)	40.89 (40.98)	7.05 (7.07)	1460 vs 1465 s	1000 vs 1020 s
2.	piperidine	388 (408)	200-205	29.16 (29.17)	44.16 (44.12)	7.58 (7.60)	1449 sd 1460 s	990 } 1005 } ^{br,s}
3.	dibutyl	430 (452)	198-200	26.34 (26.33)	47.72 (47.79)	8.59 (8.63)	1470 sd 1480 s	990 s 1010 w
4.	N-methylaniline	378 (450)	136-38	27.65 (27.67)	47.98 (47.44)	6.76 (6.74)	1455 sd 1460 s	990 s 1005 w
5.	diethyl	372 (396)	—	30.00 (30.05)	42.51 (42.42)	7.86 (7.83)	1481 vs 1460 s	990 } 1000 } ^{s,br}
6.	N-ethylaniline	425 (444)	160-65	26.76 (26.80)	48.69 (48.65)	6.92 (6.98)	1455 s 1460 w	990 s 1020 w

nature of the organic group attached to the nitrogen atom. The substitution of an alkyl group by a heterocyclic group lowers the C-N absorption frequency since the former has high electron releasing capacity while the latter is an electron withdrawing group. The co-ordination behaviour of dithiocarbamate group whether monodentate or bidentate is reflected by C-S stretching absorptions². Presence of two bands at 990 and (1010 ± 10 cm⁻¹) shows the monodentate character of the dithiocarbamate moiety^{1,3}.

In the far infrared region, asym Sn-C and sym Sn-C stretchings have been identified at 590 and 510 cm⁻¹ respectively^{4,5}. The strong intense absorption band at 370 cm⁻¹ is assigned to Sn-S stretching mode of vibration⁶.

The proton magnetic resonance spectra recorded in CDCl₃ show the presence of two groups of signals, one possessing split signals due to N-CH₂ protons at ~ 6-7τ which indicates restricted rotation about C-N bond making the two groups nonequivalent⁷ and thus supporting monodentate character of the dithiocarbamate group⁸. The second group of signal has multiplet at 8.2-9.2τ due to alkyl protons. In the case of compounds containing phenyl ring a multiplet is observed at ~2-3.5τ. The spectra and their integration agree well with the proposed stoichiometry.

The observed stoichiometry coupled with the infrared and proton magnetic resonance spectral data suggest an ester type structure for the newly synthesized compounds possessing a monodentate dithiocarbamate moiety and tetra co-ordinated tin atom.

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References

1. T. N. SRIVASTAVA and VIJAY KUMAR, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1976, **55**, 107.
2. G. E. MANOUSSAKIS, C. A. TSIPIS and C. C. HAJIKOSTAS, *Canad. J. Chem.* 1975, **53**, 1530.
3. G. ST. NIKOLOV, N. JORDANOV and K. DASKALOVA, *Inorg. Nuclear Chem. Lett.* 1970, **6**, 723.
4. F. K. BUTCHER, W. GERRARD, B. F. MOONEY, R. G. REES, H. A. WILLIS, A. ANDERSON and H. A. GEBBIE, *J. Organometal. Chem.* 1964, **1**, 431.
5. R. J. H. CLARK, A. G. DAVIES and R. J. PUDAPHAT, *J. Chem. Soc. C.*, 1968, 1828.
6. M. SCHMIDT and H. SCHUMANN, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1963, **325**, 130.
7. C. E. HOLLOWAY and M. H. GITLITZ, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1967, **45**, 2659.
8. M. HONDA, K. KOMURA, Y. KAWASKI, T. TANAKA and R. OKAWARA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1968, **30**, 3281.

Cyclic Coagulation of Surface Waters in Laterite Soils

M. R. BALASUBRAMANIAN and M. GANDHIRAJAN

Department of Chemistry,

A. C. College of Engineering & Technology,

Karaikudi-623004

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IN the place of hackneyed coagulants in water treatment, viz., alum and hydrated coppers and of the costlier polymeric analogues, a new coagulant has been found in MgCO₃ by Thompson *et al.*¹. The chief advantage claimed for this coagulant is the absence of sludge disposal problem. It can be regenerated from the sludge thus ensuring cyclic coagulation².